

Genetic variations in *Ureaplasma parvum* macrolide resistance associated genes

Tzimoula Kotrotsiou, Maria Exindari, Eudoxia Diza, Georgia Gioula, Angeliki Melidou, Nicolaos Malisiovas

Microbiology Department, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

Summary

Macrolides are widely used for the treatment of ureaplasma infections. The aim of this study was to investigate possible genetic resistance determinants in *Ureaplasma parvum* isolates with erythromycin elevated MICs. Nine *U. parvum* isolates (four isolates with MIC ≥ 8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and five isolates with MIC ≤ 8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) from urogenital specimens were studied for genetic mechanisms of macrolide resistance. 23S rRNA operons, L4 and L22 ribosomal protein genes were amplified and sequenced. The obtained sequences were compared with the respective genotype specific-reference strains. In total 15 point mutations were revealed. Isolates with elevated erythromycin MICs presented point mutations at more than one genes of Operon 1 23S-rRNA, of Operon 2 23S-rRNA, L4 and L22 protein genes. The point mutation A196G at the L22 protein gene was reported for the first time and corresponded to a change (N66D) into the amino acid sequence of the deriving protein. In conclusion, both previously recognized and novel point mutations were detected in strains with altered susceptibility to macrolides, revealing a possible correlation with resistance to macrolides.

Key words

Ureaplasma parvum, macrolides, resistance, SNP (single-nucleotide-polymorphism)

Corresponding author

Angeliki Melidou
Department of Microbiology,
School of Medicine, Aristotle University
of Thessaloniki
University Campus, 54 124, Thessaloniki
Tel. +30 2310 999103, Fax.: +30 2310 999140
Email: amelidou@med.auth.gr

Introduction

Ureaplasma spp including *U. parvum* (previously *U. urealyticum* biovar 1). and *U. urealyticum* (previously *U. urealyticum* biovar 2), have been reported to cause non-gonococcal urethritis and prostatitis in males and cervicitis, intrauterine infection, chorioamnionitis and premature birth in women.¹⁻⁷ The lack of cell wall leads to their resistance to β -lactams. Therefore the antibiotics of choice are bacteriostatic, such as tetracyclines and macrolides or bactericidal agents, such as quinolones.⁸

Macrolides such as azithromycin, erythromycin and clarithromycin are widely used in the treatment of *Ureaplasma* infections. Erythromycin, a first generation macrolide, is widely used for over 50 years against neonatal infections and clarithromycin is administered after the first trimester pregnancy, due to the toxicity of quinolones and tetracyclines to these groups of patients.⁸

Macrolides inhibit bacterial protein biosynthesis by preventing peptidyl-transferase from adding the tRNA-attached peptide to the next amino acid as well as by inhibiting ribosomal translocation.⁹ Another potential mechanism of its bacteriostatic action is the dissociation of the peptidyl-tRNA from the ribosome.⁹

Erythromycin is fastened to the entrance of the tunnel exit of the bacterial 50S subunit. Similarly to other macrolides, it binds to the center of the peptidyl-transferase (PTC) preventing the entrance of the nascent chain to the exit tunnel. Due to the presence of the antibiotic, the peptide chain production is continued only up to 6-8 amino acids, as the space left between macrolide and PTC is limited.¹⁰

The first description of resistance to macrolides was made by Palu et al. in 1989, who described the reduced input, concentration and binding of macrolides to the ribosomes of phenotypically resistant *U. urealyticum* species.¹¹ Due to the limited technical capabilities of that era, there was no further molecular analysis of the resistance.

Later molecular studies on the resistance of *U. urealyticum* species to macrolides indicated that the gene locus implicated are domain V of 23S-rRNA and L4 and L22 proteins of the bacterial ribosome.¹²⁻¹⁶ Mutations in L4 and L22 proteins' genes of 50S ribosomal subunit inhibit the binding of erythromycin, reducing its effectiveness.¹⁰ Active efflux mechanisms and methylation targets were also correlated with resistance to macrolides.¹⁷

This work aims to contribute to the study of resistance to macrolides in greek *U. parvum* strains.

Materials and methods

The sensitivity of 100 *Ureaplasma* clinical isolates was phenotypically tested with the new MYCOFAST® Revolution kit (ELITechGroup Solutions, ELITECH Group Puteaux, France), which is a commercially available assay that allows for detection, identification and antimicrobial-susceptibility testing of genital mycoplasmas within 48 hours. This assay, in accordance with the CLSI guidelines, determines MIC <8 μ g/ml for sensitive strains and MIC >16 μ g/ml for resistant ones. Out of the 100 tested isolates, four presented MICs \geq 8 μ g/ml. This study used nine clinical strains of *U. parvum* including the aforementioned non-sensitive ones, well characterized at serovar level, isolated from the urogenital tract of symptomatic or asymptomatic adults, that belonged to genotype 3 (five strains), 1 (three strains) and 6 (one strain) (Table 1). Patients enrolled in the study were 20 to 70 years old, residents of Northern Greece, with no restriction on race or nationality. During the collection of samples, patients questioned for symptoms of the urogenital tract, reporting no antimicrobial treatment during the last month for any reason.

In all nine isolates of *U. parvum* the distinction at serovar level was achieved by amplifying the Multiple Banded Antigen protein gene, using primers that amplified specific MBA protein genes of genotypes 1, 3,

Table 1 Ureaplasma strains tested for genes associated with macrolide resistance

Non-sensitive ureaplasma strains			Sensitive ureaplasma strains		
GT3/1	<i>U. parvum</i> genotype 3	♀ symptomatic	GT3/3	<i>U. parvum</i> genotype 3	♀ asymptomatic
GT3/2	<i>U. parvum</i> genotype 3	♀ asymptomatic	GT3/4	<i>U. parvum</i> genotype 3	♀ symptomatic
GT1/1	<i>U. parvum</i> genotype 1	♀ symptomatic	GT3/5	<i>U. parvum</i> genotype 3	♀ asymptomatic
GT1/1	<i>U. parvum</i> genotype 1	♀ asymptomatic	GT1/3	<i>U. parvum</i> genotype 1	♀ asymptomatic
			GT6/1	<i>U. parvum</i> genotype 6	♀ symptomatic

6 and 14 of *U. parvum*.¹⁸ The distinction at serovar level was used for the comparison of the sequences with the corresponding reference strains in order to detect polymorphisms.

In order to detect the mentioned molecular mechanisms of the midrange resistance to macrolides, after the DNA extraction (Qiagen DNA mini ki, Hilden, Germany) from broth inocula, a previously described PCR assay targeting the domain V of 23S-rRNA, as well as the genes encoding the L22 and L4 ribosomal proteins of the four strains was used. Published primers were used to amplify conserved portions of ribosomal protein L4 and L22 genes and two 23S rRNA operons (UPL4-U/UPL4-R, UPL22-R/UPL22-U, MH23S-11/UP23S-OP1, MH23S-11/UP23S-OP2R2 designed by Beeton et al).¹⁵ PCR was performed on a Peltier Thermal Cycle PTC-0200 (Biorad, Germany). PCR products were purified using Chargeswitch PCR purification kit (Invitrogen, Paisley, UK) according to the manufacturer's instructions and then sequenced (ABI 3730 Genetic Analyzer, CEMIA, Larissa, Greece). The comparison of the sequences was made with the respective reference strains, ATCC 27813 serovar 1 ABES01000001, ATCC 700970 serovar 3 AF222894.1 and ATCC 27818 serovar 6 AA2Q010000011.

The statistical method χ^2 and its variants were used. Statistics was performed with the statistical program SPSS 13.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA).

Results

Fourteen point mutations were revealed. Isolates with elevated erythromycin MICs presented ten point mutations, at more than one genes of Operon 1 23S-rRNA, of Operon 2 23S-rRNA, L4 and L22 protein genes. The point mutation A196G at the L22 protein

gene corresponded to a change (N66D) into the amino acid sequence of the deriving protein. Sensitive *U. parvum* isolates possessed five point mutations in L4 and L22 protein genes. Out of the detected point mutations one was common for sensitive and non sensitive strains.

All the genetic alterations involving ribosomal proteins L4 and L22 as well as 23S rRNA detected in the four *U. parvum* isolates with elevated erythromycin MICs and in the five sensitive isolates are shown on Table 2.

Furthermore, no correlation was observed between the presence of point mutations and clinical features (symptomatic or asymptomatic individuals).

Discussion

The first attempts correlating polymorphisms with ureaplasma resistance in macrolides include the research of Pereyre *et al.* in France.¹³ They converted susceptible strains of *U. parvum* to resistant by cultivating the selected strains in media containing subinhibitory concentrations of macrolides. The mutations found at the region II and V of the 23S-rRNA (G2056U, G2057U, A2058G), at L4 protein gene (at amino acid level: W65R, T70K, G71V) and L22 protein gene (at amino acid level: K91N, A94D) of bacterial ribosome can be prospectively detected in clinical isolates as well.

The present study refers to clinical isolates and not *in vitro* converted Ureaplasma strains. *U. parvum* isolates with altered susceptibility to macrolides were found to possess several point mutations on the ribosomal complex operons and the deriving proteins. Concerning L22 gene, two isolates with elevated MICs presented aspartic acid (D) in position 66. In the US, 6 strains out of 370 clinical isolates tested were found

Table 2 Polymorphisms of *Ureaplasma parvum* isolates

Strains	Polymorphisms			
	L4 gene	L22 gene	Operon 1 23S-rRNA	Operon 2 23S-rRNA
<i>U. parvum</i> GT3/1 NS	A81G	–	A2942G* G3079A*	–
<i>U. parvum</i> GT3/2 NS	A81G	–	A2942G* G3079A*	–
<i>U. parvum</i> GT1/1 NS	A276G T348C G94C C95G	A196G (N66D)	A2942G* G3079A*	G2414T G2942A*
<i>U. parvum</i> GT1/2 NS	–	A196G (N66D)	A2942G* G3079A*	–
<i>U. parvum</i> GT3/3 S	G287C (R96P)	–	–	–
<i>U. parvum</i> GT6/1 S	–	G361T (A121S) A406G (I136V) C422T (T141I)	–	–
<i>U. parvum</i> GT3/4 S	–	–	–	–
<i>U. parvum</i> GT1/3 S	–	–	–	–
<i>U. parvum</i> GT3/5 S	A81G	–	–	–

resistant to macrolides and one of these strains (MIC 8 µg/ml) presented asparagine (N) in the same position.¹⁶ The same research pointed out two point mutations in one resistant strain (A121S and T141I) which were only found among our sensitive strains, thus confirming the belief that they may not contribute to macrolide resistance. A more recent study by Govender *et al.*, presented fifteen different point mutations in macrolide resistant *U. parvum* strains not including the above-mentioned N66D.¹⁹

One strain with moderate susceptibility to erythromycin was found to possess four unusual point mutations in L4, A276G, T348C, G94C and C95G, however not resulting to any amino acid replacement. In the UK, Beeton *et al.* amplified and sequenced the same genes in a strain resistant to erythromycin (MIC >64 mg/L), in five strains with MIC 8 mg/L to erythromycin and in a sensitive one. No mutations were found at the 23S-rRNA operons and at L22 protein genes.¹⁵ A 6 base deletion was only detected at the L4 protein gene in the resistant strain. This deletion resulted to

the loss of the amino acids arginine and glutamine from positions 66 and 67 respectively (63KPW - KHT70 or ΔR66Q67). In the contrary, a 15bp insertion resulting in a 5-amino acid insertion in the L4 protein between positions 69 and 70 (69TGKAR70) and to a position 70 mutation (T70R) as well. None of the genes related to the binding ability and efflux mechanisms of the macrolide agents were identified in *Ureaplasma* strains.¹⁶ The present research indicates the point mutation A81G in the L4 protein gene was observed in 20% of the sensitive and in 50% of the non-sensitive strains, therefore this polymorphism does not seem to be correlated with *Ureaplasma* resistance to macrolides. As a different nucleotide is observed in the same position (81A/G) depending on the genotype, this highlights the importance of using the appropriate reference strain when comparing sequence data because of the existing variant polymorphisms.

In the present study all strains with elevated MICs to macrolides possessed the same point mutations (A2942G, G3079A) in operon 1 of 23S rRNA. Although

these mutations were located in the vicinity of the operon 1 nucleotide sequence of the 23S rRNA region, they were detected in all four non-sensitive strains and in none of the sensitive ones. Only one strain, *U. parvum* GT1/1, possessed two point mutations (G2414T, G2942A) in the operon 2 of 23S rRNA, which was not detected in any sensitive one. Resistance to macrolides has been associated with point mutations in the 23S rRNA.¹⁴ They studied 18 strains of *U. urealyticum* with different profiles of resistance to macrolides. Five of them presented a C2243N mutation (T or C) in the 23S rRNA, associated with azithromycin and roxithromycin resistance. Nine strains resistant to roxithromycin and moderately susceptible to azithromycin were found to harbour two point mutations, A2149C and A2181T. These polymorphisms were also detected in strains susceptible to macrolides (clarithromycin, azithromycin, roxithromycin, josamycin). This verifies the theory of phenotypic and genotypic diversity of strains. Furthermore, according to Xiao et al., a high level macrolide resistance is linked to a point mutation A2066G in domain V of both of the 23S-rRNA operons.¹⁶

Different results in the above mentioned studies may be due to methodological differences and geographical localization. The importance of lower pH of the culture media susceptibility to erythromycin was pointed out by several researchers.^{1,20} The pH increase from 6.0 to 6.7 increased the antibiotic susceptibility 4-8 times.

The use of a commercial, standardized kit was regarded as the most appropriate for the present study. The use of a commercial kit is solely used for antimicrobial testing before the treatment of clinical cases.²¹

Therefore the commercial kit was preferred than the MICs accurate measurement, in order to meet the needs of clinical practice. The use of more accurate techniques for the estimation of MICs and the evaluation of polymorphisms of intermediately resistant and sensitive strains in parallel with their MICs will be an interesting target for a future study.

Furthermore, according to the results of the present study, there is no correlation between the clinical symptoms and the existence of phenotypic resistance or mutations in the drug target, since strains isolated from both asymptomatic and asymptomatic patients were moderately susceptible to macrolides, possessing mutations in their chromosome as well.

The present research did not include the investigation of methylases, esterases or efflux pumps. All these dependencies, together with the study of any possible relation of the polymorphisms to resistance to non-macrolide antibiotics, inspire future additional research plans.

In conclusion, in four strains with elevated MICs to macrolides new polymorphisms were detected. The identified polymorphisms can be proposed as potential negative co-modulators of susceptibility to macrolides.

Funding

There is no specific funding received for this work.

Transparency declarations

None to declare.

Περίληψη

Γενετικές παραλλαγές των γονιδίων του *Ureaplasma parvum* των σχετιζόμενων με αντοχή στις μακρολίδες

Τζιμούλα Κοτρώτσιου, Μαρία Εξηντάρη, Ευδοξία Δίτζα, Γεωργία Γκιούλα, Αγγελική Μελίδου, Νικόλαος Μαλισιόβας
Μικροβιολογικό Εργαστήριο, Τμήμα Ιατρικής, Αριστοτέλειο Πανεπιστήμιο Θεσσαλονίκης, Θεσσαλονίκη, Ελλάδα

Οι μακρολίδες χρησιμοποιούνται ευρέως στη θεραπεία λοιμώξεων από *Ureaplasma*. Σκοπός της παρούσας μελέτης ήταν η διερεύνηση γενετικών παραλλαγών σε γονίδια στελεχών

Ureaplasma parvum με αυξημένες τιμές MIC στην ερυθρομυκίνη. Εννέα στελέχη *U. parvum* (τέσσερα στελέχη με MIC \geq 8μg/ml και πέντε στελέχη με MIC \leq 8μg/ml) μελετήθηκαν μοριακά για ανθεκτικότητα στις μακρολίδες. Το οπερόνιο 23S rRNA, τα γονίδια των ριβοσωματικών πρωτεϊνών L4 και L22 των υπό μελέτη στελεχών ενισχύθηκαν και οι αλληλουχίες τους συγκρίθηκαν με στελέχη αναφοράς αντίστοιχου γενοτύπου.

Συνολικά, 15 σημειακές μεταλλάξεις αναγνωρίστηκαν. Τα στελέχη με υψηλές MIC στην ερυθρομυκίνη διέθεταν περισσότερες της μία σημειακές μεταλλάξεις στα γονίδια στόχους. Η σημειακή μετάλλαξη A196G στο γονίδιο της πρωτεΐνης L22 και η αντίστοιχη αμινοξική αλλαγή (N66D) στην πρωτεΐνη αναφέρονται για πρώτη φορά βιβλιογραφικά.

Συμπερασματικά, σε στελέχη *U. parvum* με μειωμένη ευαισθησία στις μακρολίδες ανιχνεύθηκαν γενετικές παραλλαγές γονιδίων ήδη γνωστές αλλά και νέες, που καταδεικνύουν πιθανή συσχέτιση με ανθεκτικότητα στην συγκεκριμένη ομάδα αντιβιοτικών.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

Ureaplasma parvum, μακρολίδες, αντοχή, σημειακές μεταλλάξεις

References

1. Waites KB, Katz B, Schelonka RL. Mycoplasmas and Ureaplasmas as Neonatal Pathogens. *Clin Micr Rev* 2005;18:757-89.
2. Mandar R, Raukas E, Turk S, Koivovits P, Punab M. Mycoplasmas in semen of chronic prostatitis patients. *Scand J Urol Nephrol* 2005;39:479-82.
3. Ullmann U, Schubert S, Krausse R. Comparative in-vitro activity of levofloxacin, other fluoroquinolones, doxycycline and erythromycin against *Ureaplasma urealyticum* and *Mycoplasma hominis*. *J Antimicrob Chemother* 1999;43(C):33-6.
4. Verteramo R, Pierangeli A, Mancini E, Calzolari E, Bucci M, Osborn J *et al*. Human Papillomaviruses and genital co-infections in gynaecological outpatients. *BMC Inf Dis* 2009;9:16.
5. Cassell GH, Waites KB, Watson HL, Crouse DT, Harasawa R. *Ureaplasma urealyticum* Intrauterine Infection: Role in Prematurity and Disease in Newborns. *Clin Micr Rev* 1993;6:69-87.
6. Eschenbach DA. *Ureaplasma urealyticum* and premature birth. *Clin Infect Dis* 1993;17:100-6.
7. Viscardi RM. *Ureaplasma* species: Role in Diseases of Prematurity. *Clin Perinatol* 2010;37:393-409.
8. Centers for Disease Control (CDC). 2015 Sexually Transmitted Diseases Treatment Guidelines (<https://www.cdc.gov/std/tg2015/>)
9. Tenson T, Lovmar M, Ehrenberg M. The Mechanism of Action of Macrolides, Lincosamides and Streptogramin B Reveals the Nascent Peptide Exit Path in the Ribosome. *J Mol Biol* 2003;330:1005-14.
10. Lovmar M, Nilsson K, Lukk E, Vimberg V, Tenson T, Ehrenberg M. Erythromycin resistance by L4/L22 mutations and resistance masking by drug efflux pump deficiency. *EMBO J* 2009;28:736-44.
11. Palù G, Valisena S, Barile MF, Meloni GA. Mechanisms of macrolide resistance in *Ureaplasma urealyticum*: a study on collection and clinical strains. *Eur J Epidemiol* 1989;5:146-53
12. Gaynor M, Mankin AS. Macrolide antibiotics: binding site, mechanism of action, resistance. *Curr Top Med Chem* 2003;3: 949-61.
13. Pereyre S, Métifiot M, Cazanave C, Renaudin H, Charron A, Bébéar C. Characterisation of in vitro-selected mutants of *Ureaplasma parvum* resistant to macrolides and related antibiotics. *Int J Antimicrob Agents* 2007; 29: 207-11.
14. Wencheng X, Xiaobo M, Lu W. Transition mutations in 23S rRNA account for acquired resistance to macrolides in *Ureaplasma urealyticum*. *Microb Drug Resist* 2008;14: 183-6.
15. Beeton ML, Chalker VJ, Maxwell NC, Kotecha S, Spiller OB. Concurrent Titration and Determination of Antibiotic Resistance in *Ureaplasma* Species with Identification of Novel Point Mutations in Genes Associated with Resistance. *J Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 2009; 53: 2020-7.
16. Xiao L, Crabb DM, Duffy LB, Paralanov V, Glass JI, Hamilos DL. Mutations in ribosomal proteins and ri-

- bosomal RNA confer macrolide resistance in human *Ureaplasma* spp. *Int J Antimicrob Agents* 2011; 37: 377-9.
17. Lu C, Ye Tl, Zhu Gx, Feng Py, Ma H, Lu Rb. Phenotypic and genetic characteristics of macrolide and lincosamide resistant *Ureaplasma urealyticum* isolated in Guangzhou, China. *Curr Microbiol* 2010;61:44-9.
 18. Kong F, Ma Z, James G, Gordon S, Gilbert GL. Species Identification and subtyping of *Ureaplasma parvum* and *Ureaplasma urealyticum* using PCR - based assays. *J Clin Microbiol* 2000; 38:1175-9.
 19. Govender S, Gqunta K, le Roux M, de Villiers B, Chalkley LJ. Antibiotic susceptibilities and resistance genes of *Ureaplasma parvum* isolated in South Africa. *J Antimicrob Chemother*. 2012;67:2821-4.
 20. Kenny GE, Cartwright FD. Susceptibilities of *Mycoplasma hominis*, *M. pneumoniae*, and *Ureaplasma urealyticum* to GAR-936, dalbavancin, dirithromycin, evernimicin, gatifloxacin, linezolid, moxifloxacin, quinupristin-dalbavancin, and telithromycin compared to their susceptibilities to reference macrolides, tetracyclines, and quinolones. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 2001;45:2604-2608.
 21. Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI). Methods for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing for Human Mycoplasmas; Approved Guideline. CLSI document M43-A. Wayne PA: Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute. 2011.